

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Development strategy to enhance local agroforestry based on nutmeg in Murano village Kaimana regency west Papua province

Moholine Tumana ¹, Hendri ^{2,*} and Soetjipto Moeljono ²

¹ Forestry Science of Magister Program, Post-Graduate Program, University of Papua, West Papua, 98314, Indonesia.

² Department of Forestry, Faculty of Forestry, University of Papua, West Papua, 98314, Indonesia.

GSC Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 24(01), 062-079

Publication history: Received on 25 May 2025; revised on 30 June 2025; accepted on 03 July 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscarr.2025.24.1.0190>

Abstract

The biophysical and socio-economic potential of Murano Village and its agroforestry institutions has not been thoroughly studied, and local wisdom guides the expansion of agroforestry. This hybrid study included quantitative and qualitative methodologies. The structure and content of nutmeg (*Myristica argentea*) produced the highest IVI value, around 200. MPTS fruits, lawang wood, and masohi also contained IVI. The Shannon-Wiener diversity value (H') of 1.33 is moderate ($1 < H' < 3$). The mild category featured 16 species. Agroforestry samples have a medium aggregate evenness of species (E) of 0.48. Murano Village uses lineages and keret for social agroforestry. A more diverse nutmeg and fruit system earned US\$ 5,529.41/ha/year. Cleaning supplies and fertilisers cost the community up to US\$ 88,24. Nutmeg-based agroforestry is achievable because the B/C Ratio > 1 . IFAS and EFAS scores were 2.74 and 2.92 after SWOT analysis. Combining 8 strengths and 8 opportunities in the SO quadrant takes 64 combinations. The government needs to develop priority plans and policies to enhance the agroforestry system in Murano Village, Kaimana Regency. Farmers receive financing from the Kaimana Regency Government to foster the development of agroforestry, diversify nutmeg-based agroforestry types, develop downstream products, educate farmers, and collaborate with local universities to maintain high-quality harvests. Legality, farmer institutions, funding, marketing, and extension are government services.

Keywords: Agroforestry; Nutmeg; Species Diversity; Bio-Physic; SWOT Analysis

1. Introduction

Agroforestry is a land-use practice that involves integrating agricultural and forestry plants to generate benefits that can be used to boost a community's income. In [1,2], agroforestry is defined as an integrated land-use system that incorporates social and ecological factors. This system is achieved by combining tree cultivation with agricultural and livestock (animal) cultivation activities, both subsystemically and commercially, to ensure that plant and animal products can be obtained optimally and sustainably from a single unit of land.

Communities generally have a close relationship and reliance on the natural resources in the vicinity of the forest. Their endeavors to manage natural resources in the vicinity of the forest area are consistently initiated by positive experiences with the environment, which provides them with strong support during the implementation process. In this instance, the traditional knowledge that is transmitted from generation to generation is inextricably linked to the community's dependence on the environment, specifically forest resources. Additionally, the forest area's resources can be sustainably managed and utilized [3,4,5].

The income of farmer households in the regions of Sumatra, Kalimantan, and Sulawesi can be substantially increased by agroforestry practices, with a range of 38% to 76%. Additionally, agroforestry contributes to the preservation of food

* Corresponding author: Hendri

security and the provision of nutrition by diversifying agricultural products [6,7]. Traditional agroforestry systems, such as "mamar," in NTT, incorporate a variety of local trees and food products. This system not only ensures food security but also safeguards local biodiversity and wisdom [8]. Other research has demonstrated that agroforestry producers in Ciamis, Tasikmalaya, and Sumbawa maintain adequate food security, regardless of economic crises or pandemics. Food consumption is stabilized and diverse through the implementation of agroforestry systems [9]. Agroforestry is employed by Indigenous Papuan communities (Manokwari, South Sorong, and Fak-Fak) to manage their yards, which involves the integration of forestry vegetation with agriculture. This system enhances carbon stock potential, sustainable environmental management, food security, biodiversity and conservation, and land productivity [10].

The utilization of forest areas in Murano Village, Kaimana District, Kaimana Regency, for agricultural purposes is capable of cultivating a variety of food commodities, including bananas (*Musa paradisiaca*), sweet potatoes (*Ipomoea batatas*), tallas (*Colocasia esculenta*), cassava (*Manihot esculenta*), and vegetables. The community also cultivates plantation commodities, including coconut (*Cocos nucifera*), gaharu (*Aquilaria malaccensis*), masoi (*Cryptocarya massoia*), and nutmeg (*Myristica argentea*). In West Papua, this management is typically implemented through the establishment of Village Forests, Community Forests, Community Plantation Forests, and Customary Forests in social forestry. These practices have also been implemented in Fak-Fak and Maluku, which are centered on the superior local commodity of nutmeg [11,12].

The agroforestry development in Murano Village is conducted based on the community's existing local knowledge, and there has been no examination or analysis of the biophysical, social, and economic potential, as well as the institutional potential, of agroforestry in the area. For generations, the community has employed and passed down this local knowledge in their daily lives. Furthermore, agroforestry in the form of gardens is used as a source of inspiration and a highly intriguing model for the development of sustainable agricultural and forestry patterns that integrate economic, social, protection, soil fertility, and biodiversity conservation benefits [13]. In addition to engineering and biophysics, the development of agroforestry necessitates the formulation of government policies and regulations regarding the use of agroforestry systems, which are crucial for advancing agroforestry and sustainable forest management [14].

Agroforestry development is significant in that it has the potential to increase farmers' income, expand employment opportunities, and contribute to the economic well-being of families and regions. It is also believed to be able to address the challenges of food security, biodiversity, conservation, and community income in Murano Village. Consequently, this investigation examines the potential of biophysical, socio-cultural, economic, and institutional factors in implementing agroforestry in Murano Village, as well as the development of strategies and policies for agroforestry in the village, with the aim of managing sustainable forests [15, 16].

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study area

Murano Village is situated at an altitude of 0 to 100 meters above sea level, with coordinates of 0°20.90' to 0°40.20' South Latitude and 132°75' to 135°15' East Longitude. Murano Village neighbors Sisir Village to the west, Jarati Village to the north, Foroma Jaya Village to the east, and the Arafura Sea to the south. The soil type on a slope of 5-10% with a clay and clay structure, facilitated by karst. The average monthly rainfall is 100 mm, and the average wind speed is 4.97 knots. The average temperature is 27-28 °C, with a humidity level of 83%. The total number of households is 79, with 197 male residents and 185 female residents.

Land administration in the village is based on the level of area assigned to the lineage or "keret", which is determined by the boundaries inherited by the progenitors. Similarly, the clan determines the extent of the agroforestry system that each family manages. Accessing land use is challenging due to the presence of dense forests, gorges, and mountains in the region. Consequently, indigenous peoples exclusively oversee land situated in lowlands that are accessible for subsistence activities and economic systems, where agricultural and plantation products are utilized to meet the needs of their families. Indigenous communities also sustainably manage their land by using local knowledge that has been passed down through generations, as evidenced by the development of agroforestry based on nutmeg. This study was conducted in six significant communities: Tapnesa, Surawy, Naguasai, Nasua, Raiya, and Mejai, whose nutmeg plantations have been administered for over 30 years. The sampling plots for each nutmeg plantation were as follows: 20 m x 20 m for the tree level, 10 m x 10 m for the pole level, 5 m x 5 m for the sapling level, and 2 m x 2 m for the seedling level. Samples were collected using these plots (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Research location of nutmeg-based agroforestry

2.2. Method of data analysis

Utilizing continuous strip sampling techniques in the gardens of indigenous peoples in Marano District, the quantitative determination of species diversity is achieved through the determination of agroforestry biophysical data. Qualitative methods are employed to collect social, economic, and institutional data through semi-structured interviews that use a predetermined list of queries. The SWOT analysis employs a hybrid method that incorporates qualitative data to gather internal and external factor data from the findings of the FGD. Additionally, utilize quantitative techniques based on the Likert scale to determine the weight and scoring of strategies and policies required for the development of nutmeg-based agroforestry, drawing on indigenous practices in Murano Village.

2.2.1. Bio-physic Data

Vegetation analysis

The structure and composition of vegetation during each growth phase can be categorized into the Importance Vegetation Index (IVI) [17,18] and subsequently classified as high, medium, or low dominance using the following formula

$$\text{Density (D)} = \frac{\text{number of individuals}}{\text{area of measurement plot}} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$\text{Relative Density (RD)} = \frac{\text{density of a species}}{\text{density of all species}} \dots\dots\dots 2$$

$$\text{Frequency (F)} = \frac{\text{number of plots where a species is found}}{\text{total number of plots}} \dots\dots\dots 3$$

$$\text{Relative Frequency (FR)} = \frac{\text{frequency of a type}}{\text{frequency of all plots}} \dots\dots\dots 4$$

$$\text{Dominance (Do)} = \frac{\text{area of the base of a type}}{\text{area of the plot}} \dots\dots\dots 5$$

$$\text{Relative Dominance (RDo)} = \frac{\text{dominance of a species}}{\text{dominance of the entire plot}} \dots\dots\dots 6$$

$$IVI = RD + FR + RDo \dots\dots\dots$$

The variability patterns of abundance measurements among species are assessed using the species diversity index (H' value) in biodiversity analysis [19,20]. the species diversity index is computed using the Shannon-Wiener formula [21]:

$$H' = -\sum (p_i \times \ln p_i) \dots\dots\dots 8$$

with H: the species diversity index, \sum : the total number of species inside the community, and Pi: the proportion of species i relative to the overall number of individual species in the community (N). The H-index value requirement is categorized as follows: high (> 2.0), medium (1.6 < < 2.0), low (< 1.6), and very low (< 1.0) [22].

The total quantity of species in a community or ecosystem, irrespective of the size of any individual species population, is referred to as species richness. [23] argues that this is a critical indicator of biodiversity, particularly in terms of the species composition of a designated area. The discovery of additional species results in an increase in the richness value of a region. Evaluation criteria: species with populations exceeding 100 are classified as high category (3), species with populations between 30 and 100 as medium category (2), and species with populations below 10 as low category (1) [24].

Evenness is the degree of homogeneity in the distribution of distinct species within a community. Across all existing species, the evenness rating denotes the homogeneity of individual distribution. If all species have nearly identical populations, the evenness score will approach the maximal value of 1. If one or more species exhibit substantial dominance, the evenness score will approach zero (minimum) [25,26]. The following formula is provided for Evenness (E)

$$E = H' / \ln S \dots\dots\dots 7$$

with E: the Evenness value, H': the Shannon-Wiener diversity index, and S: the number of speciesThe E value requirements are defined as follows: <0.25 is categorized as very low, 0.26-0.50 as low, 0.51-0.75 as moderate, and 0.76-1.0 as high [27].

Social and cultural data employ semi-structured questionnaires that emphasize variables such as customary rights to ownership, indigenous knowledge in crop rotation and soil conservation, spiritual values, the advantages of agroforestry species cultivated by indigenous communities, and cultural changes resulting from external program interventions [28,29].

The economic data use B/C ratio analysis [30] using the following formula:

$$B/C \text{ ratio} = \frac{(Total \text{ Benefit})}{(Total \text{ Cost})} \dots\dots\dots 8$$

- B/C > 1, then the business is profitable, so it is worth continuing.
- B/C < 1. then the business is at a loss, so it is not worth continuing.
- B/C = 1, then the business is neither profitable nor loss (breakeven), so it is not worth continuing.

Institutional data were examined using a semi-structured questionnaire that encompassed variables related to the role of customary institutions in forest and land management, formal institutions involved, non-governmental institutions contributing, and institutions facilitating the development of agroforestry based on customary communities in Murano Village [30,31].

2.2.2. *Strategy and Policy for Local Agroforestry Enhancement*

SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunity, Threat) is a systematic process that identifies a variety of internal factors (Strengths [S], Weaknesses [W]), Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE) and external factors (Opportunities [O], Threats [T]), External Factor Evaluation (EFE) to determine the appropriate formulation and implement the most effective strategy based on the matrix in Figure 2 [32,33]. The internal strategy factor matrix (IFAS) and the external strategy factor matrix (EFAS) were employed to develop the model. The most influential factor is assigned a maximum weight of 3.00, while those deemed insignificant are assigned a weight of 1.00. The variable rating is a scale of 1 (very poor), 2 (awful), 3 (excellent), and 4 (very good). The variable with the highest influence value in comparison to the

influence values of other variables is the most influential. Agroforestry development strategies and policies are classified according to the results of the calculations included in the IFAS and EFAS matrices.

Figure 2 Quadruple matrix of IFE and EFE

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Bio-physic Data

3.1.1. Vegetation analysis

The sample for this study was drawn from six families that have been operating an agroforestry system for an extended period, specifically over 30 years. Nutmeg (*Myristica argentea*) dominated the results of the entire garden with the highest IVI value, with a value exceeding 200. Additionally, the following MPTS were discovered: masohi (*Cryptocarya massoia*), lawang (*Cinnamomum culilawan*), durian (*Durio zibethinus*), cempedak (*Artocarpus integer*), rambutan (*Nephelium lappaceum*), mango (*Mangifera indica*), matoa (*Pometia pinnata*), langsung (*Lansium parasiticum*), and coconut (*Cocos nucifera*) (Table 1).

Table 1 IVI of nutmeg-based agroforestry in Murano Village

Species	N sample	N/ha	F	D	DR	FR	DoR	INP
Tapnesa Clan								
<i>Myristica argentea</i>	16	400	1.00	48183.76	64.00	96.76	42.86	203.62
<i>Cinnamomum culilawan</i>	5	125	0.33	207.01	20.00	0.42	14.29	34.70
<i>Pometia sp</i>	1	25	0.33	31.85	4.00	0.06	14.29	18.35
<i>Theobroma cacao</i>	1	25	0.33	25.80	4.00	0.05	14.29	18.34
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	2	50	0.33	1348.41	8.00	2.71	14.29	24.99
Total	25	625	2.33	49796.82	100.00	100.00	100.00	300.00
Surawy Clan								
<i>Myristica argentea</i>	16	400	0.63	8.96	80.95	76.92	84.77	242.64
<i>Cryptocarya massoia</i>	2	50	0.03	0.24	3.17	3.84	2.27	9.29

<i>Durio zibethinus</i>	4	100	0.06	0.62	6.35	7.69	5.87	19.91
<i>Artocarpus integer</i>	3	75	0.05	0.45	4.76	5.77	4.26	14.79
<i>Nephelium lappaceum</i>	1	25	0.02	0.04	1.59	1.93	0.38	3.89
<i>Myristica fragrans</i>	1	25	0.02	0.20	1.59	1.93	1.89	5.41
<i>Citrus Sinensis</i>	1	25	0.02	0.06	1.59	1.93	0.57	4.08
Total	28	700	0.8254	10.57	100.00	100.00	100.00	300.00
Naguasai Clan								
<i>Myristica Argentea</i>	16	400	1.00	57327.63	98.99	80.00	99.12	278.11
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	1	25	0.25	509.55	1.01	20.00	0.88	21.89
Total	17	425	1.25	57837.19	100.00	100.00	100.00	300.00
Nasua Clan								
<i>Myristica argentea</i>	16	400	1.00	48946.38	95.83	57.14	98.62	251.60
<i>Lansium parasiticum</i>	1	25	0.25	223.65	1.04	14.29	0.45	15.78
<i>Nephelium lappaceum</i>	3	75	0.50	461.47	3.13	28.57	0.93	32.63
Total	20	500	1.75	49631.49	100.00	100.00	100.00	300.00
Raiya Clan								
<i>Myristica argentea</i>	16	400	0.75	73134.00	91.84	33.33	94.78	219.95
<i>Durio zibethinus</i>	1	25	0.25	2754.46	1.02	11.11	3.57	15.70
<i>Nephelium lappaceum</i>	3	75	0.25	1105.57	3.06	11.11	1.43	15.61
<i>Metroxylon sagu</i>	1	25	0.25	71.66	1.02	11.11	0.09	12.22
<i>Pandanus conoideus</i>	1	25	0.25	1.99	1.02	11.11	0.00	12.13
<i>Citrus Sinensis</i>	1	25	0.25	31.85	1.02	11.11	0.04	12.17
<i>Musa sp</i>	1	25	0.25	62.42	1.02	11.11	0.08	12.21
Total	24	600	2.25	77161.94	100.00	100.00	100.00	300.00
Mejoi Clan								
<i>Myristica argentea</i>	16	400	1.00	26752.87	88.89	50.00	98.62	237.51
<i>Durio zibethinus</i>	3	75	0.33	306.53	4.76	16.67	1.13	22.56
<i>Nephelium lappaceum</i>	1	25	0.33	62.42	1.59	16.67	0.23	18.48
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	3	75	0.33	4.54	4.76	16.67	0.02	21.45
Total	23	575	2	27126.35	100.00	100.00	100.00	300.00

High importance values distinguish the types that play a role in a community, as they are the aggregate of Relative Density (KR), Relative Frequency (FR), and Relative Dominance (DR) [34]. The dominating species (those in power) in a plant community have a high importance value index, as explained by [35]. Consequently, species with a dominant importance value index have the highest importance value index.

The implication of Table 5 is that nutmeg is highly competitive with other plants in the garden and is highly dominant in the structure and composition of the vegetation of the agroforestry system in Murano Village. Therefore, it can serve as the foundation for establishing agroforestry based on locally superior nutmeg commodities, promoting the well-being of farmers and village communities. Furthermore, nutmeg has the potential to generate substantial economic value due to its high export value and superior status as a spice commodity.

The nutmeg is an endemic species of Papua that has adapted exceptionally well to the local agroclimatic conditions in Fakfak and Kaimana. The cultivation of this plant by local communities has been a tradition for tens to hundreds of years, including in Naguasai's garden, which has lasted for 80-90 years. Consequently, nutmeg is a significant component of the cultural identity of indigenous peoples, particularly in Fakfak and Kaimana, as well as the local agroforestry system. Nutmeg is highly valued in both national and international markets, particularly for its use in spices and essential oils, from an economic standpoint. Nutmeg is the primary source of income for the communities in Fakfak and Kaimana, and it also represents the most significant contribution to the agricultural sector's exports. The local government has expressed concern about the need to elevate nutmeg to a strategic commodity of higher importance in local commodity-based development planning [36, 37, 38, 39].

The diversity of flora types in an ecosystem can be interpreted as the type of vegetation and plant composition. This is a floristic inventory of plant types that comprise a community, as determined by the results of the description [40]. The floristic list is a valuable tool for vegetation analysis, as it is one of the parameters used to ascertain the diversity of plant types within the community. At the tree level, the woody vegetation in the forest area of multiple 20 m x 20 m garden samples in Murano Village is composed of 16 species that belong to 11 families. The *Myristicaceae* family is the most prevalent family across all growth stages, with a total of 137 trees (Table 2).

Table 2 illustrates that the species diversity index (H') in the complete land area of agroforestry gardens I, II, III, IV, V, and IV is 1.33. This value falls within the moderate category, indicating that the community is characterized by a limited number of plant species and a small number of dominant species [41]. This is demonstrated by the Shannon-Wiener category, which holds the value of $1 < H' < 3$. The median category contains 16 species, as indicated by the number of species (richness). The garden sample's aggregate species evenness (E) is 0.48, which falls within the median category. This is consistent with the assertion made by [42] that the species evenness value will be low-moderate in a community where a single species dominates.

The ecological significance of this value is that the high dominance of nutmeg suggests the system's tendency to be semi-monoculture. The ecosystem is at risk of becoming more susceptible to parasites, diseases, and climate change due to the low level of functional diversity. This suggests that other species are either not developing optimally or are solely "companions" due to the moderate Evenness and high richness. According to [43] and [44], nutmeg is a primary and indispensable commodity; however, its dependence is excessively high, which may result in adverse consequences in the event of production failure. Less productive companion species suggest that the potential for agroforestry has not been fully realized. Agroforestry is designed to be more stable, productive, and sustainable by integrating primary commodities with fruit, medicinal, wood, soil protection, and other functions [45,46].

In other regions, numerous studies have been conducted on nutmeg-based agroforestry systems that incorporate coconut, areca nut, durian, and medicinal plants in Aceh Besar. These studies have yielded H' , richness, and E values of 1.4, 18, and 0.61, respectively [47]. In North Minahasa, mixed nutmeg agroforestry with fruit and wood plants also achieved H' , richness, and E values of 1.5, 21, and 0.68, respectively [48]. Consequently, the semi-monoculture nutmeg-based agroforestry in Maruno Village must be adjusted to align with the ecological perspective of agroforestry, which is associated with richness.

Table 2 H', richness and E of nutmeg-based agroforestry in Murano Village

No	Species	Family	Garden						N sample	Diversity Index				
			I	II	III	IV	V	VI		Pi	Ln Pi	Pi * Ln Pi	H'	E
			N											
1	<i>Myristica argentea</i>	Myristicaceae	16	16	16	16	16	16	96	0.70	-0.36	-0.25	1.33	0.48
2	<i>Durio zibethinus</i>	Malvaceae		4			1	3	8	0.06	-2.84	-0.17		
3	<i>Nephelium lappaceum</i>	Sapindaceae		1		3	3	1	8	0.06	-2.84	-0.17		
4	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Anacardiaceae						3	3	0.02	-3.82	-0.08		
5	<i>Cinnamomum culilawan</i>	Lauraceae	5						5	0.04	-3.31	-0.12		
6	<i>Pometia pinnata</i>	Sapindaceae	1						1	0.01	-4.92	-0.04		
7	<i>Theobroma cacao</i>	Malvaceae	1						1	0.01	-4.92	-0.04		
8	<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	Areaceae	2		1				3	0.02	-3.82	-0.08		
9	<i>Cryptocarya massoia</i>	Lauraceae		2					2	0.01	-4.23	-0.06		
10	<i>Artocarpus integer</i>	Moraceae		3					3	0.02	-3.82	-0.08		
11	<i>Myristica fragrans</i>	Myristicaceae		1					1	0.01	-4.92	-0.04		
12	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Rutaceae		1			1		2	0.01	-4.23	-0.06		
13	<i>Lansium parasiticum</i>	Meliaceae				1			1	0.01	-4.92	-0.04		
14	<i>Mtroxilon sagu</i>	Areaceae					1		1	0.01	-4.92	-0.04		
15	<i>Pandanus conoideus</i>	Pandanaceae					1		1	0.01	-4.92	-0.04		
16	<i>Musa sp.</i>	Musaceae					1		1	0.01	-4.92	-0.04		
	Total		25	28	17	20	24	23	137					

3.1.2. Socio-economic analysis

Consequently, a discrepancy exists between the national government's regulations and the municipal level's recognition of customary rights. Prolonged conflicts between indigenous peoples, the government, and corporations that possess business permits in the forestry, plantation, and mining sectors are frequently precipitated by this disparity. This conflict has the potential to cause environmental damage due to exploitation practices that disregard the sustainability of Papua's forest ecosystem and local wisdom, in addition to impacting the social and economic aspects of local communities [49, 50, 51].

Land possession is a significant issue in agricultural development, spanning from lowlands to highlands. A legacy from progenitors that has been passed down from generation to generation in Murano village is the conversion of land, including the transformation of commodities in littoral areas to highlands, for agricultural purposes. The division of land proprietorship is typically based on clan, keret, and family, as the land has historical significance. Furthermore, the land is generally allocated to the descendants of the clan bearers or patrilineal [52,53].

When relatives in the village are involved in the process of clearing land to be used as a garden, the pattern of social relations between farmers in Murano Village is evident, as they are assigned tasks based on their capabilities. Initially, the indigenous community cleared vegetation, including shrubs, supports, poles, and small trees that were unsuitable for their use. Additionally, large trees that are unsuitable for use are felled, dried, and subsequently incinerated. The apparatus employed is still simplistic, consisting of machetes, hoes, and crowbars. Additionally, some individuals employ chainsaws (tree-felling devices). The initial plants that are planted to satisfy domestic food requirements are bananas, tubers, and vegetables. After the felled timber has cured and been incinerated, it is purified. Nutmeg, cardamom, coconut, and fruits, including durian, rambutan, cempedak, mango, and bananas, are the primary sources of revenue for the community [54,55].

Income is also influenced by the cost of nutmeg-based agroforestry cultivation in each respondent's garden. Due to the necessity of producers to maintain optimal production costs, the income obtained decreases as business costs increase. The average annual cost of farming is typically between US\$ 64.71 and 88.24. The average cost of the nutmeg-based agroforestry system in Murano Village is US\$72.06. The profit received by the village community is the result of the reduction of the income obtained from these expenditures. The nutmeg agroforestry garden sample has a B/C ratio that exceeds 1, indicating that the community's efforts are still viable (Table 3) [56,57].

Table 3 B/C ratio of nutmeg-based agroforestry system in Murano Village

No	Clan	Cost (C)/year (US\$)	Income/year (US\$)	Benefit (B)/ year (US\$)	B/C ratio
1	Tapnesa	70.59	4,181.62	4,111.03	58.23
2	Surawy	64.71	5,529.41	5,464.70	84.45
3	Naguasai	88.24	2,647.06	2,558.82	29.00
4	Nasua	70.59	3,470.59	3,400.00	48.17
5	Raiya	73.53	4,782.35	4,708.82	64.04
6	Mejoi	64.71	3,970.59	3,905.88	60.36
	Total	432.37	24,581.62	24,149.25	
	Average	72.06	4,096.94	4,024.88	57.38

3.1.3. Institutional analysis

Farmer institutions in Fakfak, recognized as the hub of West Papua's nutmeg production, have been relatively well-developed, as evidenced by the existence of cooperatives like the Tomandin Cooperative and numerous farmer organizations that the Plantation Service has sponsored. These farmer groups bolster the technical capacity of cultivation, product management, and market access. Nevertheless, [58] has identified disparities between villages, where the majority of peasant groups are formal and have not been effectively fulfilling institutional functions. In the interim, the institutions of nutmeg farmers in Kaimana remain relatively feeble, with the majority of farmers continuing to operate in informal groups or individually. Farmers' bargaining position is weakened, and they face challenges in accessing government programs and broader markets due to the absence of cooperatives or special nutmeg associations. Limited assistance, low organizational capacity, and minimal support for affirmative policies significantly

contribute to the vulnerability of farmer institutions in Papua, including Kaimana, according to research conducted by [59].

The extension institution in Fakfak has been established with the availability of agricultural extension personnel who are specifically responsible for assisting nutmeg producers in multiple production center districts. Extension personnel have initiated participation in quality mentoring programs, post-harvest, and the reinforcement of farmer institutions. Nevertheless, the intensity of assistance is irregular because the ratio of extension workers to the area of nutmeg plantations and the number of producers remains far from optimal [58]. In the meantime, the number of extension workers in Kaimana remains highly restricted, and the majority lack specialized technical expertise in the field of nutmeg commodities. Consequently, initiatives to enhance farmer institutions, improve cultivation knowledge, and streamline product processing have not been fully executed. This condition is indicative of the inadequate extension system in Papua, particularly in the case of premium commodities like nutmeg.

Capital institutions in Fakfak have access to formal financial institutions, including Bank Papua, cooperatives, Village-Owned Businesses, and various capital programs, including People's Business Credit. Despite numerous producers implementing this financing scheme to establish nutmeg plantations, the primary challenges remain the administrative requirements and the need for collateral. There are still farmers who rely on the *ijon* system or loans from intermediaries, which are often detrimental to farmers [58]. The availability of capital in Kaimana is significantly restricted, with only a small number of producers having access to formal financial institutions. The majority of producers continue to depend on their own capital or informal loans, which are typically insufficient to expand nutmeg production. This limitation is partly due to the absence of socialization and support in terms of capital access [60].

In Fakfak, marketing institutions, often disguised as nutmeg sales channels, are relatively well-organized, with the presence of cooperatives, collectors, and access to national exporters. Fakfak is recognized as the hub of Papua's nutmeg marketing, which gives it superior bargaining leverage compared to other regions. Nevertheless, price fluctuations continue to pose a challenge, particularly for small producers who are not affiliated with formal marketing institutions [61]. Conversely, the marketing of nutmeg in Kaimana remains inconsistent and heavily reliant on local intermediary merchants. The absence of cooperatives or marketing associations leads to a dependence on regional markets, low selling prices, and feeble bargaining positions for producers. The nutmeg producers in Kaimana are unable to increase their income due to a lack of access to export markets or broader marketing networks [60].

3.2. Nutmeg-based Agroforestry Enhancement Strategy

3.2.1. SWOT analysis

SWOT analysis is predicated on a logic that can optimise strengths and opportunities while concurrently minimising weaknesses and threats. Using internal and external matrices, the predetermined parameters are assigned weights and ratings to determine a value (score). This value will offer guidance on the prospects for the development of agroforestry. Tables 4 and 5 illustrate the scoring outcomes for the Internal Strategic Factors Analysis Summary (IFAS) and External Strategic Factors Analysis Summary (EFAS).

Table 4 IFAS nutmeg-based agroforestry in Murano Village

SWOT	Strategic Factors	Weith	Rating	Score
Strengths	1. Farmers produce a significant amount of nutmeg	0.07	3.9	0.28
	2. The availability of a huge amount of land	0.07	3.6	0.25
	3. The motivation of farmers to develop nutmeg commodities	0.06	2.6	0.16
	4. Availability of high-quality nutmeg seeds	0.07	3.4	0.23
	5. The yields and diversity of vegetation varieties in agroforestry land	0.07	3.5	0.23
	6. The results of agroforestry are highly reliant on the impact on communities	0.07	3.5	0.24
	7. Climate and topography are supportive	0.07	3.4	0.24
	8. Nutmeg product diversification	0.07	3.4	0.22
	Total Strengths	0.54		1.86
SWOT	Strategic Factors	Weith	Rating	Score
Weaknesses	1. Technology for the production of nutmeg is not yet available	0.05	2	0.10
	2. Inadequate post-harvest management of nutmeg	0.06	1.6	0.09
	3. Insufficient human resources for nutmeg producers	0.06	2	0.12
	4. Limited agricultural capital	0.05	2.2	0.12
	5. Absence of land expansion	0.05	2.5	0.14
	6. Minimal support from technical agencies and services	0.06	2.3	0.13
	7. Lacking pruning, fertilization, fumigation, and maintenance	0.06	1.4	0.09
	8. Deficient utilization of agroforestry land	0.06	1.6	0.10
	Total Weaknesses	0.46		0.89
	Total IFAS			2.75

Table 5 EFAS nutmeg-based agroforestry in Murano Village

SWOT	Strategic Factors	Weith	Rating	Score
Opportunities	1. Nutmeg Development Program of the Kaimana District Government	0.08	3.7	0.28
	2. Extensive marketplace	0.07	3.6	0.26
	3. Availability of Agricultural Extension Workers	0.05	2.4	0.13
	4. Significant consumer interest in the demand for nutmeg as a commodity	0.08	3.6	0.27
	5. Nutmeg seed stability and its complete price	0.07	3.4	0.25
	6. Expansion of plantation land	0.07	3.6	0.25
	7. Enhancing the grade of nutmeg after harvest	0.07	3.4	0.22
	8. The application of grafting technology, among other things.	0.07	3.5	0.25
	Total Opportunities	0.55		1.91
SWOT	Strategic Factors	Weith	Rating	Score
Threats	1. Excessive production expenses	0.04	2	0.09
	2. Scarcity of high-quality nutmeg seeds	0.06	2.3	0.13
	3. Minimal counseling and training from relevant organizations	0.06	2.2	0.13
	4. Inadequate pests control	0.06	2.8	0.17
	5. Insufficient market information	0.06	2	0.12
	6. Climate change	0.05	2.6	0.14
	7. Limited innovation and abilities	0.06	2.4	0.13
	8. Lack of guidance for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises at the District and Village levels	0.06	1.9	0.12
	Total Threats	0.45		1.01
Total EFAS			2.92	

The preferred scenario will be chosen from four accessible alternatives: aggressive, competitive, cautious, and defensive, following the completion of the SWOT analysis. [62] describe the optimal strategy for enhancing nutmeg-based agroforestry in Murano Village by evaluating internal and external parameters. The appropriate matrix can be employed to assess and differentiate between internal and external components through various expression approaches. The nutmeg-based agroforestry management system of the indigenous people of Murano Village is described in the evaluation matrix. The final score of the internal factor evaluation matrix is displayed on the vertical axis. In contrast, the final score of the external factor assessment matrix is displayed on the horizontal axis. This matrix simplifies the process of selecting strategies and policies to enhance the agroforestry system that is based on nutmeg. [63].

The internal components have a cumulative score of 2.74, while the external elements have a cumulative score of 2.92, as illustrated in Tables 4 and 5. These scores determine the suitability of the nutmeg-based agroforestry system. The internal and external factor matrices, along with their respective scores, are depicted in Figure 3. The agroforestry system founded on nutmeg demonstrates its aggressive nature. Consequently, the approach strategy can be employed to capitalize on both internal strengths and external opportunities [64,65]. This enables the system to expedite the enhancement of the nutmeg-based agroforestry system in response to the vulnerabilities and threats it encounters.

Figure 3 Strategy and policy matrix

3.3. Enhancement strategy

The most significant potential for scale-up is present in nutmeg-based agroforestry systems when implemented using SO techniques. Consequently, the primary goal of this aggressive strategy is to build on existing assets and opportunities to further develop agroforestry systems based on nutmeg. Consequently, Table 6 demonstrates an aggressive approach that is the outcome of a combination of these assets and opportunities. Agroforestry system architects combined eight strength variables with eight opportunity factors to develop a total of 64 SO tactics. Nevertheless, the majority of hybrid approaches necessitate the immediate implementation of a focused acceleration program. To expedite the development of nutmeg-based agroforestry systems, stakeholders in West Papua have identified six optimal and feasible solutions [66,67]. To preserve the quality of the harvest, the Kaimana Regency Government offers support in the following areas: legality, farmer institutions, funding, marketing, and dependable extension workers. Additionally, the government encourages farmers to expand their land management through the use of various capital facilities, diversify nutmeg-based agroforestry types, and develop downstream nutmeg products. It also increases farmer capacity through regular training and collaborates with local universities to develop new technologies. These are all priority strategies and policies for accelerating nutmeg-agroforestry systems. The objective of this methodology is to enhance the aesthetic appeal, economic feasibility, socio-cultural aspects, ecological functions, food security, and forestry sector mitigation efforts [68,69,70].

Table 6 Strategy and policy to accelerate nutmeg-based agroforestry system

Internal	External
Strengths	Opportunities
Farmers produce a significant amount of nutmeg	Nutmeg Development Program of the Kaimana District Government
The availability of a huge amount of land	Extensive marketplace
The motivation of farmers to develop nutmeg commodities	Availability of Agricultural Extension Workers
Availability of high-quality nutmeg seeds	Significant consumer interest in the demand for nutmeg as a commodity
The yields and diversity of vegetation varieties in agroforestry land	Nutmeg seed stability and its complete price
The results of agroforestry are highly reliant on the impact on communities	Expansion of plantation land
Climate and topography are supportive	Enhancing the grade of nutmeg after harvest
Nutmeg product diversification	The application of grafting technology, among other things
Aggressive Strategy (SO)	
SO1 Kaimana District Government offers assistance in the form of legality, farmer institutions, funding, marketing, and dependable extension personnel	
SO2 Promote the growth of agroforestry-based land management practices among farmers, facilitated by access to diverse, adaptable, and sustainable capital resources	
SO3 Nutmeg products require downstream processing	
SO4 Diversification of agroforestry varieties based on nutmeg	
SO5 Enhancing farmer capabilities through consistent training Development of SO6 Technology in collaboration with local universities to preserve the integrity of the harvest	

4. Conclusion

Biophysical data from Murano Village's nutmeg-based agroforestry systems showed that nutmeg (*Myristica argenta*) has the most excellent structure and composition with IVI > 200. Next, IVI was found in MPTS plants like masohi (*Cryptocarya massoia*), lawang (*Cinnamomum culilawan*), durian (*Durio zibethinus*), cempedak (*Artocarpus integer*), rambutan (*Nephelium lappaceum*), mango (*Mangifera indica*), matoa (*Pometia pinnata*), langsung (*Lansium parasiticum*), and coconut (*Cocos nucifera*). The Shannon-Wiener species diversity value (H') was 1.33, falling into the moderate category ($1 < H' < 3$). The species richness was 16 moderate species. The garden sample's species evenness (E) is 0.48, which is modest. The Social Forestry method, which addresses social concerns associated with local government land management, remains unavailable. Socially, Murano Village manages agroforestry through clans and keret—the most profitable with a diverse nutmeg and fruit system at US\$ 5,529.41 per ha/year. Community costs are limited to US\$ 88.24 for cleaning equipment and fertilizers. So that the B/C ratio is > 1, the nutmeg-based agroforestry system can be maintained and grown.

The SWOT analysis indicated IFAS and EFAS scores of 2.74 and 2.92, respectively. This suggests the matrix is in the aggressive quadrant, emphasizing internal strengths and external prospects. A combination of 8 strengths and 8 opportunities requires 64 combinations. Thus, the government must identify priority strategies and policies to expedite the development of the nutmeg agroforestry system in Murano Village and Kaimana Regency. The Kaimana Regency Government provides capital facilities to encourage farmers to promote the growth of agroforestry, diversify nutmeg-based agroforestry, and process downstream nutmeg products. It also increases farmer capacity through routine training, develops technology in collaboration with local universities to maintain harvest quality, and provides legality, farmer institutions, funding, marketing, and other extension services.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

To establish an inventory of species diversity and strategies and policies to expedite the development of agroforestry, the authors are grateful to the Village Head, the regional apparatus system, community leaders, and traditional leaders who participated in the field observation of local communities' agroforestry practices based on nutmeg in Murano Village.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

Ethical approval for field data collection is consistent with the Manual for Measuring Biodiversity of Agroforestry Systems developed by the ICRAFT, 1983 and SWOT Analysis by West Virginia University, 2013.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Gold MA, Garrett HE. Agroforestry nomenclature, concepts and practices. *North American Agroforestry*. 2021 Dec 13:27-41.
- [2] Nair PR, Kumar BM, Nair VD, Nair PR, Kumar BM, Nair VD. Definition and concepts of agroforestry. An introduction to agroforestry: Four decades of scientific developments. 2021:21-8.
- [3] Achmad B, Sanudin, Siarudin M, Widiyanto A, Diniyati D, Sudomo A, Hani A, Fauziyah E, Suhaendah E, Widyaningsih TS, Handayani W. Traditional subsistence farming of smallholder agroforestry systems in Indonesia: A review. *Sustainability*. 2022 Jul 14;14(14):8631.
- [4] Tuturop A, Nugroho JD, Warawarin A. Agroforestry and climate smart agriculture to improve food security and resilience indigenous people in Teluk Patipi District Fakfak Regency West Papua Province. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 2022 Feb 1 (Vol. 989, No. 1, p. 012005). IOP Publishing.
- [5] Awazi NP. Traditional Agroforestry Practices: What Role Does Indigenous Knowledge Play?. In *Agroforestry for a Climate-Smart Future 2025* (pp. 29-72). IGI Global Scientific Publishing.
- [6] Widiyanto KH, Suharjo D, Sardjono MA. Functions and roles of agroforestry. ICRAF. Bogor. 2003.
- [7] Duffy C, Toth GG, Hagan RP, McKeown PC, Rahman SA, Widyaningsih Y, Sunderland TC, Spillane C. Agroforestry contributions to smallholder farmer food security in Indonesia. *Agroforestry Systems*. 2021 Aug;95(6):1109-24.
- [8] Njurumana GN, Ginoga K, Octavia D. Sustaining farmers livelihoods through community forestry in Sikka, East Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia. *Biodiversitas Journal of Biological Diversity*. 2020 Jul 29;21(8).
- [9] Mutia AN, Astriani N. Regulation of food estate development in forest areas to realize food security in Indonesia. *Environmental Law Development*. 2022;6(2):224-40.
- [10] Hendri H, Nugroho Jd, Rahmadaniarti A, Nurlaela N, Prabawardani S, Luhulima Fd, Gardiner C, Hematang F. Biodiversity conservation, food security, and carbon storage potential of local agroforestry practices in the Bird's Head Region of Papua, Indonesia. *Biodiversitas Journal of Biological Diversity*. 2024 Nov 30;25(11).
- [11] Kastanya IA, Tjoa M, S Hut MP, Ir Gun Mardiatmoko MP, Latumahina F, MP SH, Iskar Bone S Hut M, Aponno HE, Hut S. Impact study of social forestry in the Maluku-Papua region. *Forest Management Study Program, PPs UNPATTI*; 2019 Feb 28.
- [12] Wasongko FW, Tafalas MG, Watunglawar B. Implementation of Social Forestry Management Policy of Village Forest Scheme for Ubadari Village Community, Kayauni District, Fakfak Regency, West Papua Province. *JIP-Scientific Journal of Educational Sciences*. 2024 Mar 2;7(3):2689-709.

- [13] De Foresta H, Kusworo A, Michon G, Djatmiko WA. When gardens become forests: Typical Indonesian agroforests, a community contribution. ICRAF, Bogor. 2000;249.
- [14] Indrianti MA. Implementation Of Agroforestry System As A Sustainable Agricultural Solution In Gorontalo. 2018. National Seminar of the Faculty of Agriculture, Ichsan University, Gorontalo, 22-24 March 2018; 7 pp.
- [15] Octavia D, Suharti S, Murniati, Dharmawan IW, Nugroho HY, Supriyanto B, Rohadi D, Njurumana GN, Yeny I, Hani A, Mindawati N. Mainstreaming smart agroforestry for social forestry implementation to support sustainable development goals in Indonesia: A review. Sustainability. 2022 Jul 29;14(15):9313.
- [16] Van Noordwijk M, Roshetko JM, Murniati A, MD S, Fay C, Tomich TP. Agroforestry is a form of sustainable forest management: lessons from South East Asia. InUNFF Intersessional Experts Meeting on the Role of Planted Forests in Sustainable Forest Management Conference 2003 Mar 24 (pp. 24-28).
- [17] Nunuhitu D, Seran W, Kaho NP. Identification Of Composition, Structure, And Biodiversity Of Agroforestry Vegetation In The Community Forest Of Saenam Village, West Miomaffo District, North Central Timor Regency. Journal of Sciencetech Research and Development. 2024 Jun 30;6(1):1352-65.
- [18] Rahmadaniarti A, Beljai M, Lestari NF. Planting pattern and space utilization of home gardens of various ethnicities: Case Study in Waraitama Village, Manimeri District, Teluk Bintuni Regency. InIOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 2023 Jun 1 (Vol. 1192, No. 1, p. 012047). IOP Publishing.
- [19] Konopiński MK. Shannon diversity index: a call to replace the original Shannon's formula with unbiased estimator in the population genetics studies. PeerJ. 2020 Jun 29;8:e9391.
- [20] Roswell M, Dushoff J, Winfree R. A conceptual guide to measuring species diversity. Oikos. 2021 Mar;130(3):321-38.
- [21] Konopiński MK. Shannon diversity index: a call to replace the original Shannon's formula with unbiased estimator in the population genetics studies. PeerJ. 2020 Jun 29;8:e9391.
- [22] Bradfer-Lawrence T, Gardner N, Bunnefeld L, Bunnefeld N, Willis SG, Dent DH. Guidelines for the use of acoustic indices in environmental research. Methods in Ecology and Evolution. 2019 Oct;10(10):1796-807.
- [23] Biggs CR, Yeager LA, Bolser DG, Bonsell C, Dichiera AM, Hou Z, Keyser SR, Khursigara AJ, Lu K, Muth AF, Negrete Jr B. Does functional redundancy affect ecological stability and resilience? A review and meta-analysis. Ecosphere. 2020 Jul;11(7):e03184.
- [24] Beckmann M, Gerstner K, Akin-Fajiye M, Ceașu S, Kambach S, Kinlock NL, Phillips HR, Verhagen W, Gurevitch J, Klotz S, Newbold T. Conventional land-use intensification reduces species richness and increases production: A global meta-analysis. Global change biology. 2019 Jun;25(6):1941-56.
- [25] Hartoyo AP, Khairunnisa S, Pamoengkas P, Solikhin A, SUPRIYANTO S, Siregar IZ, Prasetyo LB, ISTOMO I. Estimating carbon stocks of three traditional agroforestry systems and their relationships with tree diversity and stand density. Biodiversitas Journal of Biological Diversity. 2022 Dec 30;23(12).
- [26] Hidayat MY. Agroforestry patterns and diversity plants in village, West Java, Indonesia. InAIP Conference Proceedings 2025 Mar 27 (Vol. 3172, No. 1, p. 020019). AIP Publishing LLC.
- [27] Tadesse E, Negash M, Asfaw Z. Impacts of traditional agroforestry practices, altitudinal gradients and households' wealth status on perennial plants species composition, diversity, and structure in south-central Ethiopia. Agroforestry Systems. 2021 Dec;95(8):1533-61.
- [28] Govind SB, Choudhary R, Deshmukh PP. Social and cultural aspect of agroforestry. Advances in Forestry and Agroforestry. 2023:209.
- [29] Prabawani B, Hadi SP, Fisher MR, Warsono H, Dewi RS, Ainuddin I. Socioeconomic perspective of agroforestry development in Central Java. Environmental and Sustainability Indicators. 2024 Jun 1;22:100354.
- [30] Nuddin A, Arsyad M, Putera MI, Nuringsih N, Teshome TT. Making the case for institutional support on designing agroforestry technology models for rehabilitating critical lands. Forest and Society. 2019 Apr 23;3(1):49-63.
- [31] Valdivia CB, Gold MA, Barbieri C, Gao J, Flora CB. Human and institutional dimensions of agroforestry. North American Agroforestry. 2021 Dec 13:489-519.
- [32] Esfandiari S, Dourandish A, Firoozzare A, Taghvaeian S. Strategic planning for exchanging treated urban wastewater for agricultural water with the approach of supplying sustainable urban water: a case study of Mashhad, Iran. Water Supply. 2022 Dec 1;22(12):8483-99.

- [33] Idie A, Maturbongs RA, Tanujaya B, Marwa J. Urban green space development plans and strategies in Sorong city Southwest Papua Province. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*. 2023;20(1):1156-65.
- [34] Budiastuti MT, Purnomo D, Setyaningrum D. Agroforestry system as the best vegetation management to face forest degradation in Indonesia. *Reviews in Agricultural Science*. 2021;10:14-23.
- [35] Jihad AN, Lestari LD. An overview and future outlook of Indonesian agroforestry: A bibliographic and literature review. *InE3S Web of Conferences 2021 (Vol. 305, p. 07002)*. EDP Sciences.
- [36] Musaad I, Djuuna IA, Attamimi N. Land characteristics and their relationship to Papua nutmeg (*Myristica argentea* Warb.) population in Fakfak regency. *International Journal of Applied Environmental Sciences*. 2016;11(4):957-66.
- [37] Wahyuni S, Bermawie N. Yield and fruit morphology of selected high productive Papua nutmeg trees (*Myristica argentea* Warb.). *InIOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 2020 (Vol. 418, No. 1, p. 012032)*. IOP Publishing.
- [38] Naisin MA, Asyik MF. Empowerment Strategy for Nutmeg Farmers in Improving the Quality of Nutmeg Plants by the Plantation Service in Fakfak Regency. *Minangkabau Government Applied Journal*. 2022 Jun 25;2(1):73-91.
- [39] Department of Agriculture of Kaimana Regency. *Strategic Plan for Development of Regional Superior Commodities 2022–2026*. Kaimana: Kaimana Regency Regional Government 2022.
- [40] Udawatta RP, Rankoth LM, Jose S. Agroforestry and biodiversity. *Sustainability*. 2019 May 21;11(10):2879.
- [41] Bajigo A, Tadesse M. Woody species diversity of traditional agroforestry practices in Gununo watershed in Wolayitta zone, Ethiopia. *Forest Research*. 2015;4(4):2168-9776.
- [42] Hartoyo AP, Karimatunnisa TA, Ikhfan AN, Wijayanto N, Azizah S. Vegetation structure, composition and diversity in agroforestry system in Andongrejo Village, Jember Regency, East Java. *InIOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 2020 Feb 1 (Vol. 449, No. 1, p. 012017)*. IOP Publishing.
- [43] Tjokrodiningrat S, Ashari S, Syekhfani S, Aini N. The characteristics of nutmeg (*Myristica fragrans* Houtt) growth using agroforestry system in Ternate Island, Indonesia. *Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences*. 2016;58(10):13-23.
- [44] Salampessy ML, Febryano IG, Zulfiani D. Bound by debt: Nutmeg trees and changing relations between farmers and agents in a Moluccan agroforestry systems. *Forest and Society*. 2017 Nov 27;1(2):60-6.
- [45] Utomo B, Prawoto AA, Bonnet S, Bangviwat A, Gheewala SH. Environmental performance of cocoa production from monoculture and agroforestry systems in Indonesia. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 2016 Oct 15;134:583-91.
- [46] Prayogo C, Arfarita N. The conversion of monoculture sugarcane to a tree-based agroforestry system increases total carbon sequestration and soil macrofauna population. *Journal of Degraded and Mining Lands Management*. 2022 Oct 1;10(1).
- [47] Hayati D, Fahmy Armanda MJ, Rosita I, Muhammad A. Traditional Agroforestry Practices (Lampoh) In Aceh Besar: Assessing The Potential And Utilization By The Community In Simpang Tiga District. *Jurnal Agriment*. 2023 Jun;8(1):74-80.
- [48] Kogoya Y, Walangitan HD, Kainde RP. Agroforestry Mixed Garden Pattern in Warembungan Village, Pineleng District, North Sulawesi Province. *In Cocos 2017 (Vol. 9, No. 6)*.
- [49] Resubun ML. *Don't Destroy My Home: Save Papua*. Nomaden Institute; 2019.
- [50] Kusumaryati V. Freeport and the states: Politics of corporations and contemporary colonialism in West Papua. *Comparative Studies in Society and History*. 2021 Oct;63(4):881-910.
- [51] Mahendra JR. Development Policy vs Indigenous Peoples' Rights: Resource Conflict and Violence in Papua. *InProceeding National Conference of Research and Community Service Sisi Indonesia 2025 Jun 17 (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 100-114)*.
- [52] Sudayasa IM, Frank SA, Rumansara EH. Shifting Traditional Leadership Systems in the Indigenous Community of Ayapo Village, Jayapura Regency. *Cenderawasih*. 2021;2(2):99-119.
- [53] Tekege P, Rahanra RM. Papua people and its culture. *Lakhomi Journal Scientific Journal of Culture*. 2022 Sep 13;3(3):89-99.

- [54] Shanika KR, Ramadhan AI, Varadilla A, Pinasti NA, Tari NV, Handriza SA. Nature Sustainability Threatened by Multinational Corporation Cooperation: Land Clearing in Papua in 2020. *PROIROFONIC*. 2025 Jan 3;1(1):100-9.
- [55] Parirak A, Nugroho B, Siburian RH. Socio-economic characteristics of agroforestry system in village of Batulubang Region of Sorong, West Papua.
- [56] Sinaga A, Suddin AF, Amar MA. Potential increase in cocoa production through vegetative propagation in Papua Barat Province. *Agricultura*. 2019;3(4):110-5.
- [57] Maftu'ah E, Susilawati A, Sulaeman Y. Agroforestry for restoration of degraded peatlands. In *E3S Web of Conferences 2021* (Vol. 305, p. 03001). EDP Sciences.
- [58] Fakfak Regency Plantation Service. Fakfak Nutmeg Plantation Annual Report. 2023; Fakfak: Fakfak Regency Government.
- [59] Dhiaulhaq A, McCarthy JF. Indigenous rights and agrarian justice framings in forest land conflicts in Indonesia. *The Asia Pacific Journal of Anthropology*. 2020 Jan 1;21(1):34-54.
- [60] Central Statistics Agency of Kaimana Regency. Plantation Statistics of Kaimana Regency in 2022. 2023; Kaimana.
- [61] Kompas. Fakfak Nutmeg That Gives Life. *Kompas Exploration*. 2021, June 21); Retrieved from <https://www.kompas.id/>
- [62] Tamrin M, Baguna FL, Kamaluddin AK, Tamnge F, Ibrahim PY. Strategy Development Of Agroforestry at Campus IV Khairun University, Bangko Hamlet, West Halmahera Regency. In *Proceeding International Conference Khairun University 2024 Jun 10* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 97-101).
- [63] Chairani A, Sakti PJ, Irfal I, Pangkerego ER. Increasing the Competitiveness of Sweet Nutmeg and Papaya Products Owned by MSMEs in Cibeber Village, West Java Province, Indonesia. *BASKARA: Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship*. 2025 Apr 30;7(2):156-66.
- [64] Sirajudin N, Ridwan M, Malamassam D. Agroforestry development strategy in West Halmahera Regency, North Maluku. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies*. 2021;4(4):117-25.
- [65] Adhy MT, Kamaluddin AK. Agroforestry Management in the Community Empowerment Block of KPH Bacan, South Halmahera Regency. *Wahana Forestra: Forestry Journal*. 2022 Jul 27;17(2):135-47.
- [66] Novasari D, Wulandari C, Harianto SP, Febryano IG, Bakri S, Kaskoyo H. Community preferences for agroforestry patterns in supporting future forestry development. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 2023* (Vol. 1133, No. 1, p. 012066). IOP Publishing.
- [67] Purwanto P, Yuliana CI, Sambodo MT, Nadjib M, Yaumidin UK, Hidayat S, Suryanto J, Hidayatina A, Rahmayanti AZ, Handoyo FW, Astuty ED. Towards a New approach to community-based rural development: Lesson learned from Indonesia. Available at SSRN 4911244. 2023 Oct 3.
- [68] Hakim L, Siswanto D, Rahardi B, Zayadi H. Fostering coffee agroforestry for agrotourism development in degraded land in a buffer zone of a national park: A case study from Poncokusumo, Malang, Indonesia.
- [69] Penot E, Chambon B, Wibawa G. An history of rubber agroforestry systems development in Indonesia and Thailand as alternatives for a sustainable agriculture and income stability. In *Proceedings of International Rubber Conference 2017 Oct 4* (pp. 1-26).
- [70] Sudomo A, Leksono B, Tata HL, Rahayu AA, Umroni A, Rianawati H, Asmalayah, Krisnawati, Setyayudi A, Utomo MM, Pieter LA. Can Agroforestry Contribute to Food and Livelihood Security for Indonesia's Smallholders in the Climate Change Era?. *Agriculture*. 2023 Sep 27;13(10):1896.